

TECHNOLOGIES OF IMPROVING SPIRITUAL-EDUCATIONAL WORK IN
INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF PEDAGOGICAL PROFESSIONAL SKILLS

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Аннотация

Мазкур мақолада таълим жараёнида педагогик касбий маҳоратни ривожлантиришнинг муҳим омилларидан бири сифатида маънавий-маърифий фаолиятнинг аҳамияти таҳлил этилади. Хусусан, маънавий-маърифий ишлар самарадорлигини ошириш мақсадида жорий этиладиган замонавий технологиялар – ахборот-коммуникация, аксиологик, интерактив ва шахсга йўналтирилган технологияларнинг мазмуни, қўлланиш механизми ва педагогик самараси кенг ёритилади. Шу билан бирга, ушбу технологияларнинг ўқитувчи касбий маҳоратига таъсири ва уларни педагогик амалиётда татбиқ этиш имкониятлари илмий жиҳатдан асослаб берилади.

Калит сўзлар: педагогик маҳорат, маънавий-маърифий фаолият, таълим технологиялари, интерактив усуллар, аксиологик ёндашув, шахсга йўналтирилган таълим, ахборот-коммуникация технологиялари, педагог тайёргарлиги, замонавий таълим, тарбиявий жараён.

Аннотация

В данной статье рассматривается значимость духовно-просветительской деятельности в повышении эффективности педагогического профессионального мастерства. Подробно анализируются современные технологии, используемые для совершенствования данной деятельности, включая информационно-коммуникационные технологии, аксиологический подход, интерактивные методы и личностно-ориентированное обучение. Также в статье освещается вклад этих технологий в развитие профессиональной компетентности педагогов и их роль в формировании духовно-нравственного мировоззрения учащихся.

Ключевые слова: педагогическое мастерство, духовно-просветительская деятельность, образовательные технологии, интерактивные методы, аксиологический подход, личностно-ориентированное обучение, информационно-коммуникационные технологии (ИКТ), подготовка педагогов, современное образование, нравственное воспитание.

Abstract

This article explores the importance of spiritual and educational activities in enhancing the effectiveness of pedagogical professional skills. It provides a detailed analysis of modern technologies used to improve these activities, including information and communication technologies, axiological approaches, interactive methods, and learner-centered education. The paper also examines how the application of these technologies contributes to the development of teachers' professional competence and their role in shaping the spiritual and moral worldview of students.

Keywords: pedagogical competence, spiritual-educational activity, educational technologies, interactive methods, axiological approach, learner-centered teaching, information and communication technologies (ICT), teacher training, modern education, moral development.

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In today's era of globalization and information, life itself confirms that the socio-economic development of each country depends, first of all, on the direction in which its education system is developing. In particular, the central figure of the education system is the teacher. A modern teacher is an important person not only in providing education, but also in ensuring the moral, intellectual and spiritual development of students. From this point of view, the effectiveness of pedagogical professional skills is directly related to the content and form of spiritual and educational activities. The effective use of new technologies, innovative approaches and interactive methods by a teacher in his work serves to improve his professional skills. In this regard, improving spiritual and educational work in the educational process and organizing them on the basis of modern technologies is of great importance. The concept of pedagogical professional skills is determined not only by the possession of theoretical knowledge by a teacher, but also by the ability to effectively apply them in practical activities. To acquire such skills, a teacher must constantly work on himself, study new pedagogical technologies and introduce them into the teaching process. In this case, spiritual and educational work serves as an important educational tool. Because the formation of the spiritual world, moral views, and social responsibility of students requires a high spiritual culture, broad thinking ability, and dedication from the teacher. Therefore, spiritual and educational work should be considered one of the main tasks in improving pedagogical professional skills.

In order to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in today's educational process, a number of modern technologies are used. Among them, information and communication technologies, axiological approaches, interactive methods, and personally oriented educational technologies are of particular importance.

Today, modern information and communication technologies (ICT) are becoming an important tool in increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the education system. In particular, through multimedia resources, online platforms, and e-learning content, materials with spiritual and moral content are delivered in a fast, comprehensive, and interesting way. These technologies are effective in increasing the speed of students' thinking, forming the ability to analyze independently, and teaching them to communicate in a cultural way. For example, spiritual projects implemented through platforms such as "ZiyoNet" and "Kundalik.com" provide interactive communication between teachers and students, helping to deepen their understanding of educational concepts[1]. In addition, the spiritual and educational education process is organized in an effective and emotionally rich way with the help of video lessons and audiovisual materials.

Online forums and webinars are important in forming a culture of communication among students, teaching them to exchange ideas and respect the diversity of opinions. Visual presentation of spiritual topics through multimedia presentations is quickly and effectively reflected in the minds of students.

E-books, e-articles and digital educational content allow for the individualization of the educational process, which ensures that each student acquires spiritual knowledge in accordance with his or her own potential and interests. In addition, interactive tests, online competitions and problem questions provide an opportunity to analyze and evaluate spiritual knowledge.

Effective integration of ICT tools into spiritual and educational activities, along with the development of pedagogical professional skills, serves to enrich the content and form of the educational process in accordance with modern requirements.

Axiology is a doctrine about values, which plays an important role in the personal and social life of people. In pedagogy, with the help of axiology, the effectiveness of the processes of forming

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and educating national, universal and moral values in the educational process is increased. By clearly and concisely explaining the content of spiritual values in lessons and connecting them to real-life realities, the teacher serves to awaken students' spiritual awareness and responsibility towards society.

Pedagogical technologies based on the axiological approach are aimed at developing human qualities in students, such as values of justice, love, patience, discipline and responsibility. These technologies serve not only to provide knowledge, but also to improve the personality, to educate it as a socially active citizen. At the same time, the axiological approach enriches the teaching process, encourages students to study their attitude to spiritual values and life norms, to analyze them, to think[2]. The application of axiology in the educational process ensures that pedagogical professional skills are more complete and effective. In this way, the teacher methodologically improves his spiritual and educational work and helps the spiritual and moral development of students through interactive and innovative methods. As a result, not only the students' scientific knowledge, but also their personal qualities and social responsibilities are strengthened. The effective introduction of axiological technologies into the education system is one of the important directions for improving pedagogical professional skills and significantly improves the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work.

Interactive educational technologies are one of the most effective methods for strengthening spiritual and educational education. Through methods such as exchange of views, debates, "case studies", role-playing games, creative problem solving, students become active participants[3]. This forms in them the ability to think independently, critically analyze and responsibly approach social relations.

Spiritual and educational activities organized taking into account the individual potential, interests and level of knowledge of each student make a great contribution to their personal development. After all, each student should be considered as a unique person, and from this point of view, the educational process must be organized in accordance with his internal needs.

A person-centered approach requires the teacher to implement differentiated and individualized education. This creates the opportunity to provide effective spiritual and moral education through a deep study of the student's personality, taking into account his interests, level of education, life experience and psychological characteristics.

Through this type of pedagogical technology, students not only receive knowledge, but also strive to understand themselves, assess their capabilities, make independent decisions, take an active life position and find a worthy place in society. For example, tasks aimed at maintaining a personal portfolio, organizing reflection, and finding solutions to problem situations create an environment for students aimed at personal growth.

This approach creates a spiritual environment for students to develop themselves, strive for spiritual maturity and freely express their thoughts. Also, a person-oriented approach is important in improving pedagogical professional skills, as it increases the teacher's ability to reconsider his work style, use new approaches, and take an individual approach to each student.

A person-oriented approach is an effective means of enriching the content of spiritual and educational work, stimulating the spiritual development of students, and educating a person useful to society.

From the above thoughts and considerations, it can be concluded that spiritual and educational work plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of pedagogical professional skills. Combining this activity with modern technologies increases its effectiveness and efficiency several

times. The application of information and communication, axiological, interactive, and person-oriented technologies in spiritual and educational work ensures not only the level of knowledge of students, but also their spiritual maturity. Training and retraining of pedagogues on the basis of these technologies, supporting their activities on scientific and theoretical bases is an important guarantee of raising a competent generation in the future.

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